

Designing and Deploying a FAIR Resource Portal for Geospatial Data

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Abstract—In recent years, the need for FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data portals has become increasingly important for effective utilization of the wealth of data that is being generated through growing access to computational resources. Despite this growing demand, there are currently no canonical open-source solutions available for FAIR-compliant resource data portals. This paper reports on our preliminary results in trying to address this critical gap by providing a practical implementation strategy for deploying FAIR-compliant portals. Specifically, this paper presents our experience in designing and systematically implementing a FAIR-compliant resource portal for geospatial data. The paper outlines the system architecture, including the high-level design, data resource management, and metadata extraction processes.

Index Terms—FAIR,portal,gateway,geospatial

I. INTRODUCTION

The FAIR data principles proposed in 2016 [1] have gained broad acceptance and importance in data management strategies for research projects. At the same time, a variety of FAIR evaluation tools have been designed [2] that can help evaluate the FAIR compliance of a particular data portal. However, gateway (and more specifically, data portal) developers still lack clear guidelines on how to implement these principles in practice. Existing solutions for data portals often fall short in fully adhering to FAIR principles, particularly in terms of interoperability and reusability.

Our project aims to address these gaps by developing a FAIR-compliant resource portal specifically designed for geospatial data¹. While our focus on geospatial data is in response to the needs of a resource management portal for managing workflow outputs from the GeoEDF workflow engine [3], we believe that our portal design and implementation strategies can be adapted for any other scientific domain.

The development of this portal involved several key steps, including the design of a robust system architecture around an extensible open source portal framework, the integration of domain-specific metadata extraction and standardization, and the implementation of features that ensure adherence to FAIR principles. We describe each of these steps in the following sections and conclude with a summary of the lessons learned during our implementation.

II. BACKGROUND

A. GeoEDF

The Extensible Geospatial Data Framework (GeoEDF) [3] is designed to reduce the amount of effort geospatial researchers spend in wrangling data for their research workflows. GeoEDF provides a plug-and-play workflow engine that enables researchers to integrate data acquisition and processing operations into their workflows through community-contributed, reusable workflow building blocks termed “data connectors” and “data processors” respectively. GeoEDF also seeks to support the FAIR principles by enabling researchers to publish both their workflows and the workflow outputs to a data portal where other researchers can discover and reproduce these workflows. Rather than utilize an existing geospatial data portal such as Hydroshare [4], the GeoEDF team sought to develop a FAIR-compliant portal from the ground up in order to systematically identify the components of FAIR compliance and the means to address each of these requirements. The portal described in this paper is the result of this endeavor.

B. Metadata Schema

A key component of FAIR compliance is the use of a structured metadata schema to describe the hosted datasets. Common schemas used in describing data include Schema.Org, ISO 19115 and Dublin Core. These schemas provide standardized elements for documenting various aspects of data. We selected Schema.org for our portal due to its rich semantics and flexibility for geospatial data [5]. ISO 19115 while highly formalized and comprehensive is not specifically designed for web applications. Dublin Core although more web-friendly, lacks specific geospatial properties and hierarchical structures that are useful for describing complex resources [6]. In contrast, Schema.org supports detailed properties like spatial coverage, making it suitable for comprehensive geospatial data descriptions. Its ability to embed elements allows us to represent a resource with multiple files as a single, coherent entity. Additionally, Schema.org’s adoption by Google enhances the discoverability of datasets. Its established framework ensures consistency and interoperability [7].

¹<https://geoedf-portal.anvilcloud.rcac.purdue.edu/>

C. Globus Modern Research Data Portal

The first step in designing the data portal was identifying a suitable extensible open-source portal framework that could serve as the baseline for further customization. We chose the Globus Modern Research Data Portal [8] both due to its extensibility as well as its integration with Globus authentication, data management, and search. Globus Auth, the authentication system, integrates with institutional single sign-on services for secure access and privacy compliance. Globus Search enhances data discoverability with advanced indexing and search capabilities based on metadata, content, and queries. Furthermore, since the portal is based on the Django framework, this readily provides a collection of tools that can be used to implement other features such as a data publication API.

III. PORTAL DESIGN

The system architecture of our data portal is shown in Figure 1 and illustrates the custom-developed components as well as existing services and tools that have been leveraged in our implementation. At its core is a customized Globus Django Data Portal that serves as the central hub, managing a set of searchable published data resources through integration with a Resource Database and a dedicated Globus Search Index. Each published data resource has a dedicated resource landing page, which displays detailed metadata (including where available, spatial coverage) and includes embedded Schema.org metadata for indexing via web crawlers, leading to enhanced web searchability. Resource publication is primarily via a publication API that can be invoked from a variety of client interfaces such as an external JupyterHub or a built-in file manager. On invocation, the publication API triggers asynchronous metadata extraction and indexing to Globus via the RabbitMQ message broker and a scalable set of Resource Metadata Extractor workers. The FAIRness Evaluator assesses published resources for compliance with the FAIR principles. Finally, the portal integrates with Google, allowing it to crawl and index resources, thus displaying rich results in search queries.

A. Resource Management

We define a resource as any dataset or file collection that users wish to publish and share. We categorize resources into three types to streamline their management and metadata extraction:

- **Geospatial Files:** This type includes vector and raster files with geospatial data. For these files, we extract metadata such as geospatial coverage and projection information which can be used in search and display.
- **Workflow:** This category includes resources related to GeoEDF workflows, which is a design specific to the GeoEDF project. In order to enable reproducibility, these resources include workflow input files (if any), the workflow definition file in the YAML format, and the workflow output files. The resulting resource is packaged as a single

zip file, with metadata being extracted for each of the components.

- **General Files:** This type includes all other datasets that do not fall into the previous categories. These files can include various types of research data, and we extract general metadata such as file type, size, and descriptive information provided by the user.

The Resource Database manages administrative information about each resource such as the uniquely assigned resource ID, the user requesting its publication, and its publication status as it goes through the process of metadata extraction and registration in the Globus Search Index.

B. Metadata Extraction

The metadata extraction process is designed to extract metadata from various file types and submit it to Globus, ensuring resources are well-described and discoverable. A resource publication request via the publication API results in a message routed to the RabbitMQ broker. Using RabbitMQ for asynchronous communication prevents the loss of publication requests, which might occur due to the long processing time for large files or errors from external services. Asynchronous processing enhances fault tolerance and reliability, ensuring that the system can handle long-running tasks and recover from failures without losing data.

A scalable set of metadata extraction workers continuously listen for new messages on the configured RabbitMQ queue. Upon receiving a message, the corresponding resource files are processed to extract and assemble metadata in the Schema.org format and submitted to Globus Search via the use of the Globus SDK. Periodic polling is utilized to enquire the status of the metadata ingestion into Globus Search, which is then updated in the Resource Database.

C. Making the Portal FAIR

As a first step to ensuring the FAIRness of the data portal, we sought to ensure that each “findable” resource (that has a unique resource identifier) has sufficient discoverable metadata in the resource landing page reachable via its unique identifier. Additionally, we also sought to implement a rich resource API that will support programmatic metadata discovery as well as integration with external tools.

1) *Embedded Schema.org metadata:* Resource metadata is compiled into a Schema.org JSON by mapping the extracted metadata to corresponding Schema.org properties. The resulting Schema.org JSON-LD metadata is then embedded directly into the HTML source of the landing page of each resource using Django derived templates. To ensure that the embedded metadata is recognized and validated by Google, our implementation follows the documentation and guidelines provided by Google Dataset Search [9]. The key elements included in the Schema.org object are basic information such as name, size, and modification time; unique identifiers for findability; a detailed description providing contextual information; information about the resource creator; geospatial and

Fig. 1. System Diagram illustrating the custom-developed components (blue) and leveraged services and tools (green).

temporal coverage details; URLs for accessing the resource and downloading it; and licensing details promoting reuse.

2) *Resource API*: The Resource API complements the data portal and is designed to support programmatic management and discovery of the published resources and their metadata. Token-based authentication is used for access control and to verify user identity before performing certain data operations. The API supports various operations, including publishing resources and retrieving metadata. Parameters are logically arranged for easy parsing and processing to ensure clear user interaction with the API².

IV. PORTAL DEPLOYMENT

In order to ensure scalability and portability, the portal and associated components (such as the metadata extractor) are deployed using Docker containers and Kubernetes orchestration in Purdue’s Anvil composable cloud. Docker image builds for the portal and metadata extractor are automated through GitHub Actions to streamline the CI/CD process and push container images to the Anvil composable cloud’s Harbor registry. The various deployment files and configurations are available in our public GitHub repositories [10, 11].

V. FAIRNESS EVALUATION

To further ensure the FAIRness of the data portal, we next applied a data-driven, systematic approach to improving its quantitative score using well-known FAIRness evaluators.

A. Evaluator Selection

In assessing various FAIRness evaluators we tested three tools: F-UJI [12], FAIRsharing [13], and FAIRshake [14]. While each evaluator had its strengths, F-UJI proved to be the most mature in automatically assessing aspects of FAIR

compliance with well-developed assessment metrics as well as providing detailed feedback on missing elements that impact the assessment score.

B. Evaluation Result

The evaluation results obtained from F-UJI are presented in a structured JSON format, which includes metric identifiers, names, outputs, statuses, and scores for a total of 16 FAIR evaluation metrics. In order to perform a systematic improvement of our data portal, we first carried out a preliminary evaluation following our initial implementation. This evaluation revealed gaps in persistent identifiers, comprehensive metadata, and integration with semantic resources, resulting in a FAIR compliance score of 47% (Figure 2). After implementing targeted improvements to address these specific areas, the portal’s score increased to 60% (Figure 3), reflecting the positive impact of these enhancements on FAIR compliance.

Broadly, there are certain key considerations in ensuring FAIRness as revealed by the evaluation. In terms of findability, our portal effectively uses globally unique identifiers and supports metadata retrievability. However, there is room for improvement in the use of persistent identifiers and comprehensive descriptive metadata. For accessibility, the portal show full compliance in providing secure data and metadata access through network protocols, ensuring clear and reliable data access conditions. Regarding interoperability, the use of JSON-LD for metadata structuring of linked and composite resources is effective. When it comes to reusability, our portal satisfies requirements in data content specification and clear licensing for reuse.

VI. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENTS

Based on the evaluation, we identified several areas of future improvement to enhance the FAIR compliance of our portal.

²<https://geoedf-portal.anvilcloud.rcac.purdue.edu/swagger>

Fig. 2. FAIR evaluation report on the initial version

Fig. 3. FAIR evaluation report on the enhanced version

The implementation of these enhancements varies in difficulty but is crucial to improving the portal’s alignment with FAIR principles. We briefly summarize the changes that will have the most impact on the FAIRness score:

- 1) Using established persistent identifier providers such as DOI, w3id, URN, or PURL is a key aspect of findability.
- 2) Ensuring that metadata explicitly includes core descriptive elements (creator, title, object identifier, publication date, publisher, object type, summary, and keywords) is another key aspect of findability.
- 3) Interoperability requires having multiple methods for metadata access. Including methods such as content negotiation, typed links, or SPARQL endpoints will improve the interoperability score.
- 4) Incorporating additional semantic resources such as DCAT2 which is a RDF vocabulary designed to facilitate interoperability between web-based data catalogs is a key area of improving interoperability.
- 5) Discrepancies between the file size in the metadata and the actual downloaded size impact the reusability score.
- 6) Detailed provenance tracking including the resource’s editing history is another key factor in the reusability score.

While it can be argued that an overemphasis on the quantitative FAIRness score of a data portal takes away from the usability and domain or project-specific features and capabilities, we believe that having an agreed upon FAIRness evaluator and a community-driven implementation of capabilities that can ensure FAIR-compliant portals would be a valuable baseline for the science gateways community. While we do not claim to have solved this challenge, we hope that this paper provides some useful ideas for other gateway developers who need to design a customized data portal that solves a domain need, while also ensuring adherence to the FAIR principles.

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